

1 **Efficient removal of mercury (II) from water by use of cryogels and comparison**
2 **to commercial adsorbents under environmentally relevant conditions**

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11
12 **Abstract**

13 Mercury is a toxic element, which can be found in air, water and soil in several inorganic
14 and organic forms. Mercury pollution comes from a variety of industrial sources, including
15 vinyl-chloride industry, pulp and paper, fertilizers, pharmaceuticals, gold mining and cement
16 production. Gels have increasingly attracted the interest over the past decades and one of the
17 applications is the fast removal of organic substances, metals and other cations and anions from
18 water. In this work, two types of cryogels were synthesized at sub-zero temperatures by free-
19 radical polymerization technique, characterized by using a set of complimentary methods and
20 used for the removal of mercury from aqueous solutions of different chemistry. Kinetics and
21 equilibrium studies were performed in ultra-pure water solutions in order to study the
22 mechanisms in the presence nitrate and chloride ions. The cryogels exhibited excellent efficiency
23 towards mercury removal from model solutions of different chemistry. Moreover, the cryogels

24 were tested in different water matrixes (tap, river and sea water) and compared to commercial
25 adsorbents (activated carbon, strong acid resin and zeolite Y). Cryogels were able to remove
26 mercury much faster than commercial adsorbents with the exception of seawater where activated
27 carbon was superior.

28

29 *Keywords:* cryogels; adsorption; speciation; mercury; water matrix

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Water pollution with heavy metals, especially mercury in its organic and inorganic forms,
33 is a serious worldwide ecological challenge. Although natural sources, such as volcanoes, forest
34 fires, mercury minerals deposits and volatilization from the ocean contribute, the dominant share
35 of mercury emissions comes from man-made sources [1–3]. According to United Nations
36 Environment Program [4] the anthropogenic sources are responsible for more than 2,220 tons of
37 mercury in air in 2015. The majority of the pollution originates from small-scale gold mining
38 (38%), coal combustion (21%), non-ferrous metals production (15%), cement industry (11%)
39 and ferrous metal manufacturing (2%). Chlor-alkali industry used to be one of the biggest
40 emitters but the technology is gradually phased-out [5]. Several studies have pointed out that the
41 artisanal and small-scale gold mining cause more mercury pollution than any other industry [6].
42 Although an ancient technique, is unfortunate that mercury amalgamation of gold is still in use in
43 many poor regions of Asia, Africa and South America endangering the health of workers and the
44 general population. This situation it is developing into an environmental and human health crisis.

45 The removal of mercury from water is a crucial environmental issue due to the adverse
46 effects on humans and ecosystems [7]. Especially toxic are the organic forms of mercury

47 produced via microbial activity, which are bioaccumulate and biomagnify mercury concentration
48 into the food chain. It has been reported that mercury compounds in general are more toxic than
49 compounds of any other non-radioactive heavy elements [5]. Consumption of water
50 contaminated with mercury may affect the neurological and mental functions of the humans,
51 leads to dizziness, irritability, anorexia, hypertension, tachycardia and memory loss and affects
52 the digestive and renal systems [8–10]. The serious health consequences of consuming mercury-
53 poisoned fish and water have been long recognized, especially after the Minamata accident in
54 Japan [11]. As a result, several regulatory measures were taken worldwide and for instance, the
55 US Environmental Protection Agency established a maximum acceptable concentration of
56 mercury ions at 1 and 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in drinking and wastewater, respectively [12,13]. More
57 importantly, on August 16th 2017, the Minamata Convention on Mercury was ratified by more
58 than 50 parties to the treaty [6]. By the time the treaty enters into force, new Hg mining will be
59 banned and any Hg mines in operation must be closed within 15 years from that date [5].

60 Various methods for mercury removal from water have been used, including
61 reduction/volatilization, membrane separation, precipitation, adsorption, ion exchange,
62 macroalgae and bioremediation [14,15]. Among these methods adsorption exhibits several
63 advantages in terms of operational simplicity and cost effectiveness. There is a variety of suitable
64 materials and the selection of an adsorbent with desirable properties for Hg^{2+} removal is
65 challenging [12]. Example of materials used for the removal of Hg^{2+} from water include:
66 activated carbons [16], zeolites [17,18], resins [19] and silver-impregnated materials, such as
67 alumina, zeolites, graphene [18,20,21] and synthetic polymers [22,23]. Recently, a new class of
68 polymers made from elemental sulfur as a starting material have shown great promise in mercury
69 removal [24–29]. A comprehensive review on emerging materials and technologies is provided

70 by Wang et al. [15]. Table 1 presents studies on several adsorbents and the achieved maximum
 71 removal capacity.

72 **Table 1**
 73 **Adsorbents used for the removal of mercury from water.**

Adsorbent type	Initial Hg ²⁺ concentration (mg/L)	Initial pH	Hg ²⁺ compound	Maximum removal capacity (mg/g)	Reference
SiO ₂ -carbon nanotubes	40	7.0	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	142	[30]
Au-Al ₂ O ₃	0.4	7.0	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	676	[31]
Ag- Fe ₃ O ₄	1.6	8.0	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	42	[32]
Ion exchange resin TP-214	100	-	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	456	[19]
Chitosan-p(vinyl alcohol) cryogel	374	3.5	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	374	[33]
P. chrysosporium loaded cryogel	100	6.0	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	88	[34]
AAC cryogel	100	3.7	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	742	This study
SAC cryogel	100	3.7	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	676	
AgNP@ mercaptosuccinic acid on alumina	2	5.0	Hg(O ₂ CCH ₃) ₂	800	[20]
Chitosan-p(vinyl alcohol) cryogel	668	5.5	Hg(O ₂ CCH ₃) ₂	668	[33]
Chitosan-p(vinyl alcohol) cryogel	2070	5.5	Hg(O ₂ CCH ₃) ₂	586	[35]
Ag NPs-impregnated synthetic zeolites	10	2.0	HgCl ₂	1.3	[17]
Activated carbon	150	6.0	HgCl ₂	29	[36]
Jute nanofiber	10	6.0	HgCl ₂	85	[37]
Thiopolymer	2000	-	HgCl ₂	65	[27]
Sulfur-hydroxylated triglyceride copolymer	107	-	HgCl ₂	2.3	[29]
Synthetic zeolite-AgNP	10	2.0	HgCl ₂	6-22	[18,38]
Ag/graphene	100	5.0	HgCl ₂	281	[21]
Cd/S- polycaprolactam	20	7.0	HgCl ₂	162	[39]
Single wall carbon nanotubes- thiol groups	30	5.0	HgCl ₂	131	[40]
Mesoporous silica- ammonium (4-chloro-2-mercaptophenyl) carbamodithioate	2	5.5	HgCl ₂	164	[41]
Flower-like nanotitanate	50	5.0	HgCl ₂	454	[42]
Fe ₃ O ₄ -SiO ₂ -thiol groups	50	3.0	HgCl ₂	90	[43]
Graphene-diatom silica aerogel	100	6.5	HgCl ₂	500	[3]
Sulfur-modified activated carbon	100	5.0	HgCl ₂	75	[16]
Chitosan-p(maleic acid) hydrogel	2000	6.0	HgCl ₂	1044	[22]
Chitosan-p(vinyl alcohol) cryogel	468	5.5	HgCl ₂	184	[33]
Thiol-grafted p(GMA) polymer	300	7.0	HgCl ₂	51	[44]
p(EGDMA-VIM)] hydrogel	200	5.0	-	163	[45]
Polyethyleneimine cryogels	100	7.0	HgCl ₂	1280	[46]
AAC cryogel	100	4.99	HgCl ₂	263	
SAC cryogel	100	4.99	HgCl ₂	240	This study

74 Macroporous cryogels have been considered as alternative adsorbents for the removal of
 75 mercury from water [45]. Cryogels are hydrophilic sponge-like materials with 3D macroporous

76 polymeric matrices produced at sub-zero temperatures [47,48]. By selecting the monomers
77 different specific functional groups can be embedded in the polymer, e.g. -OH, -NH₂, -CONH₂, -
78 SO₃H and -COOH for effective and targeted elimination of heavy metals from water [49–51]. In
79 addition to fast removal and high sorption capacity, the wide modifiability and possibility of
80 regenerating and reusing the cryogels is an additional advantage [50,52,53]. Due to their serious
81 environmental impact several approaches have been utilized for the elimination of heavy metals
82 from water [54–56], but only limited number of studies investigated macroporous cryogels
83 [34,45,46].

84 This paper reports the synthesis of two novel macroporous cryogels synthesized by free-
85 radical co-polymerization of acrylate-based precursors with allylamine under sub-zero
86 temperature conditions. The allylamine-methacrylic acid cryogel named as AAC (Acrylic Acid
87 Cryogel) is a co-polymer of methacrylic acid, allylamine, dimethylacrylamide and
88 methylenbisacrylamide. The second cryogel named as SAC (Sulfonic Acid Cryogel) is based on
89 allylamine-2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propansulfonic acid and it has similar chemical
90 composition of monomers and concentrations with AAC cryogel, but methacrylic acid was
91 replaced with 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propansulfonic acid. The cryogels were fully
92 characterized and studied for the removal of mercury from solutions of mercury chloride and
93 nitrate salts. To the best of our knowledge, the studies on the removal of mercury by gels are
94 scarce and there are no studies on the type of cryogels used in this study. Furthermore, there are
95 no studies on the performance of gels under different aqueous phase mercury speciation. This is
96 of particular importance when it comes to the application of these materials in contaminated
97 natural waters, where, for instance, inorganic mercury is complexed to organic ligands such as
98 humic matter [24]. Kinetics and equilibrium studies are presented, models are applied and in

99 combination to post-sorption characterizations potential removal mechanisms are discussed.
100 Notwithstanding the importance of fundamental studies, before cryogels can be considered for
101 large-scale applications they must be compared to commercial adsorbents under real conditions.
102 For this purpose, the materials were tested in real waters (tap, river and sea) spiked with Hg^{2+}
103 and compared to the efficiency of commercial adsorbents (activated carbon, zeolite and ion-
104 exchange resin).

105

106 **2. Materials and methods**

107

108 *2.1. Materials*

109 The chemicals used for the synthesis of the cryogels (Sigma-Algrich, Germany) were;
110 N,N-dimethylacrylamide (DMAAm, 99%), 70% H_3PO_4 , NaOH, allylamine (AA) (98%), N,N-
111 Methylenebis (acrylamide) (BisAAm, 99%), 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid
112 (AMPS), methacrylic acid (MAAc) (99%), ammonium peroxodisulfate (APS, 98%) and
113 N,N,N',N'-Tetramethyl ethylene diamine (TEMED, $\geq 99.5\%$). Two mercury salts were used,
114 namely HgCl_2 and $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ of purity of $\geq 99\%$ and ultra-pure water was used for the
115 preparation of the solutions (Puris MR-RO1600, Mirae ST).

116

117 *2.2. Cryogels synthesis*

118 The cryogels were synthesized by the free-radical polymerisation technique by BisAAm
119 cross-linking in degassed ultra-pure water [57]. Degassed ultra-pure water was prepared by
120 purging N_2 through it for 30 min. The quantities of the reagents used for AAC and SAC cryogels
121 synthesis are provided in Table S1. Briefly, MAAc for AAC and AMPS for SAC cryogels and
122 BisAAm were added to degassed ultra-pure water under vigorous stirring to achieve complete

123 solubilisation followed by alkalisation by 5 M NaOH to neutralise acid. Another solution was
124 prepared containing monomers of DMAAm and AA dissolved in degassed ultra-pure water
125 under continuous stirring and acidified by concentrated H₃PO₄ to convert allylamine into a
126 phosphate salt. Subsequently, after mixing these two solutions, degassing was carried out for 30
127 min and TEMED was added drop-wise and cooled down to 2-4 °C for 30 minutes under nitrogen
128 atmosphere followed by the addition of 5 wt% of APS under stirring. Finally, 2 mL of the
129 monomeric mixture was transferred into plastic syringes of 1 cm of diameter, which were
130 immediately sealed to avoid dissolution of oxygen from air in the solution and to prevent
131 inhibition of radical polymerisation. The syringes were immersed in ethanol-cooled program-
132 controlled cryobath (Julabo F34, Germany) and kept at -12 °C for 24 hours. The obtained
133 monolithic cryogels were thawed in warm water (23-25 °C) and washed, firstly with 1% ethanol
134 and then with 2 L of pure water. The water was removed from the cryogels structure prior further
135 characterization and experiments by freeze-drying using a FreeZone 2.5 L (Labconco, USA)
136 lyophile drier at -53 °C and 0.4 mbar for 48 h.

137

138 *2.3 Characterization of materials*

139 The morphological characteristics of polymers were investigated by using a Zeiss
140 Crossbeam 540 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) at 3 kV, equipped with a backscattered
141 electron detector. An Energy-Dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrometer (INCA X-sight, Oxford
142 Instruments) connected to SEM was used for spot (point) and area (mapping) elemental analyses.
143 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were conducted on a VG-Microtech
144 Mutilab 3000 device equipped with a 9 channeltrons hemispherical electron analyzer and X-ray
145 radiation source with Mg and Al anodes. The binding energies (BE) were calibrated by using the

146 C1s core level at 284.8 eV. For FTIR analysis the lyophilized samples were prepared as fine
147 powders. Infrared spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹,
148 using a Cary 600 Series FTIR spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies) equipped with an
149 ATR module. Zeta potential was studied by batch equilibration method. A mass of 10 mg of
150 polymer was immersed in 10 mL of aqueous solution at initial pH from 2 to 9 adjusted by adding
151 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH and keeping the ionic strength constant. The solutions were
152 equilibrated for 24 h by shaking at room temperature [58]. Zeta potential was studied using a
153 Zetasizer Nano (Malvern, UK) instrument. The total nitrogen of parent and mercury-containing
154 cryogels was determined by DuMaster D-480 (Buchi, Switzerland) analyser using aspartic acid
155 of purity ≥99.5% (Sigma-Aldrich) for calibration.

156

157 *2.4 Cryogel swelling capacity*

158 The cryogels were sliced into 10 mm diameter monoliths and used for determination of
159 the swelling capacity. A mass of w_o (g) of cryogel was weighted and immersed in a 200 mL
160 sealed glass flask containing ultra-pure water at ambient temperature. At specific time intervals
161 the cryogel was withdrawn from water and its surface was gently wiped to remove excess water
162 and weighed to obtain the weight w_t (g). This procedure was repeated until the weight remained
163 constant. The swelling (S) was calculated as follows:

$$164 \quad S = \frac{w_t - w_o}{w_o} \quad (1)$$

165

166 *2.5 Batch adsorption kinetics*

167 A volume of 100 mL of 100 mg/L mercury HgCl₂ or Hg(NO₃)₂ solution without pH
168 adjustment was added in plastic tubes containing 0.08 g of cryogels under 120 rpm shaking and

169 ambient temperature. After definite time intervals 0.1 mL of sample was withdrawn from the
170 solutions for analysis. The total sampling volume was below 3% of the initial volume. To
171 determine the total mercury concentration in the solution a RA-915 M mercury analyzer (Lumex,
172 Russia) with a pyrolysis technique was used. Blank solutions of the same mercury concentration
173 without cryogels were also used. The amount of mercury adsorbed was calculated as follows:

$$174 \quad q_{eq} = \frac{C_o - C_f}{m} \times V \quad (2)$$

175 where q_{eq} is the amount of mercury adsorbed (mg/g), m is the weight of the cryogel (g), V is the
176 volume of solution (L) and C_o the initial and C_f the final mercury concentrations (mg/L) in the
177 solutions. The mercury losses due to adsorption on tube walls and evaporation as measured by
178 blank experiments were less than 3%. All experiments were carried out in duplicate and the
179 average standard deviation was 2.4%. The release of sodium ions from cryogels in the absence of
180 mercury was investigated by placing 80 mg of dry cryogel in 100 mL of ultra-pure water under
181 120 rpm shaking and ambient temperature for 14 days. The release of Na^+ ions from both types
182 of cryogels was no more than 1 mg/g. The released sodium ions during mercury sorption were
183 analysed by atomic absorption spectroscopy by use of AAnalyst 400 instrument (Perkin-Elmer,
184 USA).

185

186 *2.6 Adsorption isotherms*

187 An amount of 0.0025 to 0.1 g of cryogel was mixed with 100 mL of mercury solution in
188 batch mode. The solutions were under 120 rpm shaking (Rotamax 120, Heidolph) at ambient
189 temperature. Samples were withdrawn periodically and measured for mercury until no
190 concentration change was observed. The pH and conductivity were monitored by using Mettler

191 Toledo meter and probes. The experiments were conducted in duplicate and average values are
192 reported. The average standard deviation was 1.9%.

193

194 *2.7 Leaching experiments*

195 The evaluation of the retention of mercury on the cryogels was performed in leaching
196 experiments at pH 7. Ultra-pure water was used to remove the residual mercury from the surface
197 of the solids after the adsorption experiments and the containers were tightly closed and left
198 under 120 rpm shaking at ambient temperature. After 14 days the solutions were analysed for
199 mercury. All tests were performed in duplicate.

200

201 *2.8 Removal of mercury ions from different water matrices by cryogels and commercial* 202 *adsorbents*

203 The adsorption studies were conducted in batch mode by dissolving 10 mg/L Hg²⁺ in
204 different water matrices by using 200 mg/L Hg(NO₃)₂ stock solution. Ultra-pure water (Puris
205 MR-RO1600 (Mirae ST, South Korea)), tap water (tap water from Nazarbayev University labs),
206 river water (43°15'04.0"N 76°51'50.7"E, Bolshaya Almatinka, Almaty, Kazakhstan) and natural
207 seawater (38°20'54.0"N 0°28'23.5"W, Alicante, Spain) were used without any further
208 purification. For the removal experiments commercially available activated carbon (GUNT,
209 Germany), ion-exchange resin (strongly acidic, H⁺-form, Merck), synthetic zeolite (sodium Y
210 zeolite, Sigma Aldrich) and synthesized AAC and SAC cryogels were used. A mass of 0.1 g of
211 each material was mixed with 50 mL of 10 mg/L Hg(NO₃)₂ solutions made by using different
212 water matrix at room temperature. Samples were withdrawn at 10 min, 1 h, 4 h and 24 h and the
213 residual mercury was measured by a mercury analyzer. Also, the cations and anions in the

214 solutions were measured by a Dionex ICS 6000 ion chromatography system (Thermo Scientific,
215 USA) after filtering through 0.45 μm hydrophilic filter and dilution. The experiments were done
216 in duplicate and average values are reported. The average standard deviation was 3%.

217

218 **3. Results and discussion**

219

220 *3.1. Synthesis and Characterization*

221 An illustration of the AAC cryogel cryopolymerization reaction is shown in Fig. 1. First,
222 a complex of allylamine with phosphoric acid and neutralization of acrylic acid was formed.
223 Previously allylamine was copolymerized with methacrylic acid under cryoconditions, which
224 characterized by low yield of gel fraction [59], which was related to low activity of allylamine
225 radical polymerization process. According to literature, in order to improve the activity of allyl
226 monomer in the radical polymerization process it is necessary to convert it to a phosphate
227 complex [60,61]. Simultaneously to the radical polymerization of selected monomers, cross-
228 linking of polymeric chains is taking place producing branched macromers and growth of ice-
229 crystals occur expelling all components of the reaction mixture into non-frozen liquid
230 microphase, where radical polymerization continue until the monomers are consumed or the
231 polymerization is terminated [59]. Upon the completion of the polymerization reaction and
232 solvent thawing, the breakdown of the 3D structure of microcrystals leads to macro-sized pores
233 formation within the polymeric material.

234

235

Fig. 1. Cryogels synthesis schematic representation.

236

237 During the synthesis of polymers, one of the most important stages is the correct

238 selection of the ratios of monomers, cross-linkers and initiators of the reaction. The crosslinking

239 agent is particularly important in the formation of the elastic polymer matrix; therefore, different

240 monomers/cross-linking agent (BisAAm) mole ratios have been tested. It was found that the

241 optimal ratio of monomers to BisAAm is 10:1. The possible reaction of formation of AAC and

242 SAC cryogels are presented in Fig. 2A and 2B respectively.

245 **Fig. 2.** Possible reaction of formation of AAC (A) and SAC (B) cryogels.

246 The FTIR spectra are shown in Fig. 3, where the various functional groups in the
 247 cryogels structure are depicted.

249

250 **Fig. 3.** FTIR spectra of AAC and SAC cryogels.

251 Both cryogels have peaks at approximately 3300 cm⁻¹ attributed to the stretching
 252 vibration bands of N-H group and 2900 cm⁻¹ corresponds to sp³ hybridized -CH-CH₂ and -CH₃

253 groups. Amide(I) and amide(II) groups were identified at 1621-1610 and 1560-1540 cm^{-1} ,
254 respectively [35]. On AAC cryogel stretching vibrations bands of dissociated and non-
255 dissociated carboxyl group were observed at 1141 cm^{-1} and 1390 cm^{-1} , respectively [20]. The
256 characteristic frequencies of sulfonic acid at 1452-1401 cm^{-1} , sulfoxide at 1186 cm^{-1} , sulphide at
257 1035 cm^{-1} and C-S functional groups at 619 cm^{-1} were identified on SAC cryogel, originated
258 from the sulphur-containing monomer used for the synthesis [62–64].

259 The zeta potential results are presented in Fig. S1. At pH higher than 3.2 the surface
260 charge of AAC cryogel is negative due to protonation of carboxyl groups, while the SAC cryogel
261 surface is negatively charged for the whole pH range due to the dissociation of sulfonic acid . It
262 can be assumed that the aminogroups of allylamine are protonated and form intermolecular
263 polyelectrolyte complex with neighbouring sulfonic groups and carboxyl groups. A decrease of
264 negative zeta potential for AAC at pH above 6 is probably related to the deprotonation of the
265 ammonium groups. The positive charge of AAC at pH below 3.2 is attributed to positively
266 charged aminogroups of polyallylamine. Therefore, at pH below 3.2 negatively charged ions will
267 be adsorbed but cations can also be removed via ion exchange mechanism.

268 SEM microphotographs revealed the three-dimensional network associated with super-
269 macroporous and interconnected channels of cryogels with pores of size from 10 to 100 μm (Fig.
270 4). The spot elemental analysis confirmed that the mass percentage of carbon, oxygen and
271 nitrogen is approximately the same for AAC and SAC cryogels. An amount of sodium is
272 detected as expected due to the use of NaOH in the synthesis, while sulfur is detected in the
273 structure of SAC cryogel due to the AMPS monomer used in the synthesis (Table 1).

274

275

276 **Fig. 4.** SEM and elemental composition according to spot EDX analysis of the AAC (A, C, E)

277

and SAC (B, D, F) cryogels.

278

Swelling experiments showed that both cryogels rapidly adsorbed water in 1-2 seconds.

279

The swelling degree for AAC cryogel reached 22.5 gH₂O/g cryogel, while SAC cryogel

280 exhibited slightly lower degree of swelling of 19.5 gH₂O/g cryogel. This fast swelling is due to
281 the super-macroporous structure of the cryogels.

282

283 3.2. Adsorption kinetics

284 Fast removal is particularly desirable in emergency situations, especially when toxic
285 substances such as mercury are involved. The results of the kinetics experiments are illustrated in
286 Fig. 5. As it is clear, mercury removal is rapid and after 2 h AAC and SAC cryogels remove
287 about 91% and 73% of mercury from Hg(NO₃)₂ solution and 64 and 40% from HgCl₂ solution,
288 respectively. Both cryogels removed 99% of mercury ions within 24 h from 100 mg/L solutions
289 and use of a small amount of material (80 mg in 100 mL of solution). An exception is the SAC
290 in HgCl₂ solution, which reached equilibrium within 48 h with removal level of 81.5%. As it is
291 clear, AAC cryogel is superior, while removal from Hg(NO₃)₂ solution is faster for both
292 cryogels. The potential mechanisms are discussed in section 3.4.

293

294

295

296

Fig. 5. Kinetics results (80 mg of cryogel in 100 mL of solution).

297

To further study the mechanism of removal, the pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-

298

order models were applied on the experimental data. The linear forms of these models are as

299

follows [22,65]:

300

$$\ln(q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (3)$$

301

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (4)$$

302

where q_e and q_t is the amount (mg/g) of Hg^{2+} adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (min),

303

respectively. The pseudo-first-order constant k_1 (min^{-1}) and q_e^{cal} can be obtained from the slope

304

and intercept of the $\ln(q_e^{\text{exp}} - q_t)$ versus time graph (Fig. S2(A)). The pseudo-second-order

305

constant k_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) and q_e^{cal} can be calculated from the t/q_t versus time graph (Fig.

306

S2(B)). The modeling results are given in Table 2. Also, q_e^{exp} is the experimental value of q_e

307

308 **Table 2**

309 Kinetics modeling results.

	q_e^{exp} (mg/g)	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order		
		q_e^{cal} (mg/g)	K_1 (min^{-1})	R^2	q_e^{cal} (mg/g)	K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	R^2
AAC-HgCl ₂	123.3	88.1	0.2704	0.9669	121.9	0.0079	0.9926
SAC-HgCl ₂	101.9	78.4	0.1958	0.9835	94.3	0.0164	0.9945
AAC-Hg(NO ₃) ₂	122.6	58.8	0.8436	0.9628	126.6	0.0022	0.9996
SAC-Hg(NO ₃) ₂	122.7	95.7	0.5177	0.9937	142.8	0.0080	0.9994

310

311 As it is evident, the pseudo-second order model better fits the experimental capacity data
312 as the correlation coefficient is higher than the pseudo-first order. The pseudo-second order
313 model assumes that the rate-limiting step involves chemical interactions leading to the binding of
314 ions to the solid's surface by strong covalent bonds [66]. When applied on adsorption systems,
315 the basic assumption of the reaction kinetics-based models is that mass transfer is fast enough to
316 be neglected. Thus, these models are applicable in chemisorption on solids that are either non-
317 porous or porous exhibiting high diffusion coefficients and, from this point of view, suitable for
318 cryogels [66].

319 The presence of mercury on the cryogels surface was proved by semi-quantitative
320 mapping EDX analysis and is shown in Fig. S3-S6. The results showed that all samples have
321 mercury on the surface and the amount varies from 4.56 to 10.2% w/w. The EDX mapping
322 analysis images reveal that mercury ions are distributed evenly over the entire surface of the
323 polymers. The nitrogen content reduction after mercury adsorption is discussed in paragraph 3.4.
324 Finally, the cryogels were tested for Hg^{2+} leaching and the results showed that maximum loss
325 was 0.2% for both HgCl_2 and $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ experiments (Table S2). This demonstrates strong
326 binding of Hg^{2+} on the surface of the cryogels.

327

328 **3.3 Adsorption equilibrium**

329 The experimental isotherms are shown in Fig. 6. The removal from the $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
330 solution is more efficient reaching much higher solid phase loading (Fig. 6). In the $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
331 solution cryogels show the same efficiency and the shape of the isotherm is the same. In the
332 HgCl_2 solution AAC is superior and the isotherms are different. These results are in agreement
333 with the kinetics experiment and also show that the interactions between the cryogels and

334 mercury in the $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution are similar in both cryogels. On the other hand, in the HgCl_2
 335 solution the interactions are markedly different. The potential mechanisms are discussed in more
 336 detail in section 3.4.

337

338

339 **Fig. 6.** Isotherms of mercury removal by cryogels.

340 In order to study further the experimental isotherms, Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm
 341 models were applied, both widely used for the description of adsorption of heavy metals on the
 342 homogeneous or heterogeneous surfaces, respectively. The linear form of Langmuir
 343 isotherm [22,67] is:

$$344 \quad \frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_m K_L} + \frac{C_e}{q_m}, \quad (5)$$

345 where C_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium mercury concentration in the solution phase, q_e and q_m are
 346 the equilibrium and maximum mercury loading on the solid phase in mg/g and K_L is the
 347 Langmuir constant (L/mg). The linear form of Freundlich isotherm is [68]:

$$348 \quad \log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (6)$$

349 where C_e (mg/L) and q_e (mg/g) is the solution phase concentration and solid phase loading at
 350 equilibrium and n (dimensionless) and K_F constants (units depend on the $1/n$).

351

352 **Table 3**

353 Equilibrium modeling results.

	Langmuir model				Freundlich model		
	q_{\max}^{exp} (mg/g)	q_m (mg/g)	K_L (L/mg)	R^2	n	K_F	R^2
AAC-HgCl ₂	262.2	263.2	0.8261	0.9992	0.1758	131.6	0.7501
SAC-HgCl ₂	174.0	212.8	0.0484	0.9948	0.3787	33.3	0.9966
AAC-Hg(NO ₃) ₂	626.5	666.7	0.6667	0.9312	0.4338	83.6	0.9713
SAC-Hg(NO ₃) ₂	622.5	666.7	0.0568	0.9073	0.4464	78.4	0.9837

354 The experimental data are better represented by the Langmuir isotherm for both cryogels
355 in HgCl₂ solution and the derived maximum capacities are close to the experimental (Table 3).
356 Despite the fact that the correlation coefficient of the Freundlich model (0.97-0.98) is higher than
357 for the Langmuir model (0.90-0.93) for the Hg(NO₃)₂ solution, the capacities derived from
358 Langmuir model are very close to experimental values. The good fit of Langmuir model
359 indicates a monolayer adsorption of mercury on the surface of cryogels.

360 The adsorption capacity of both cryogels in Hg(NO₃)₂ solution is high, up to 626 and 622
361 mg/g by AAC and SAC cryogels, respectively, and comparable to other reported values for
362 cryogels. Privar et al synthesized polyethyleneimine cryogels with different crosslinking agents
363 for adsorption of Hg²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions from water. The maximum adsorption capacity for Hg²⁺
364 was observed for the cryogel crosslinked by diglycidyl ethers at 1,280 mg/g [46]. Wang et al
365 used chitosan-p(vinyl alcohol) cryogel for adsorption of mercury from solutions prepared by
366 using different salts [33]. The results showed that at pH 5.5 for HgCl₂, pH 5.5 for Hg(CH₃COO)₂

367 and pH 3.5 for $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solutions the cryogel samples reached a maximum adsorption capacity
368 of 184, 668 and 374 mg/g, respectively [33]. Ge and Hua synthesized chitosan-poly(maleic acid)
369 hydrogel crosslinking by glutaraldehyde for the removal of various heavy metals from water. For
370 Hg^{2+} ions the maximum capacity was 1,044 mg/g at pH 6 [22]. In another study, Ge et al.
371 changed maleic acid to itaconic acid and examined polymers ability to remove Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+}
372 ions. The experiments showed a maximum Hg^{2+} loading of 870 mg/g [69]. Finally, Li et al.
373 modified chitosan-polyacrylamide polymer by $\text{SiO}_2@Fe_3O_4$ nanoparticles and used parent
374 polymer and synthesized composite for removing Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions. The initial polymer
375 showed maximum loading of 88.5 mg/g, while the modified samples reached a maximum
376 loading of 264 mg/g [70].

377 While the rapid kinetics and high capacity of cryogels are attractive properties, the
378 complexity and cost of synthesis can be problematic for large-scale production but they can be
379 considered for small-scale production and uses, such as emergency spills, and biomedical
380 applications. Other applications can be tap water and small-scale water treatment [71]. On scale-
381 up, Andrabi et al. studied the cleaning of wastewater in a 6.5 cm height and 7 cm diameter
382 cryogel column [56]. The results showed that the chitosan-dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate
383 (DMAEMA)-magnetite filter can be of low cost and was efficient for the removal of microbes,
384 chromium and arsenic from water. Jo et al. used polyvinyl alcohol cryogel as biocarriers in
385 nitritation and anammox treatment of low-strength ammonia wastewater, a process intended for
386 large-scale municipal wastewater treatment [72]. Savina et al. studied a simple method for the
387 production of large volumes of cryogels for biotechnological, medical and environmental
388 applications [73]. According to this study, macroporous gels of up to 400 ml bulk volume were
389 manufactured, with potential for scale up to much larger dimensions. Finally, another important

390 aspect relevant to practical applications of cryogels is regeneration. A regeneration efficiency
391 after the removal of several heavy metals of 56-97% can be achieved by using EDTA, HNO₃ or
392 Na₂(EDTA) solutions [48]. Experiments on Hg²⁺-loaded cryogels are necessary to study
393 regeneration in more detail.

394

395 **3.4 Mechanisms of removal**

396 The functional groups of cryogels can participate in ion exchange and several chemical
397 reactions rendering the removal mechanism of mercury complex [46]. Before discussing what is
398 happening on the surface, it is important to understand the aqueous chemistry of mercury, i.e. its
399 speciation. For this purpose, Medusa software was used to study the speciation in HgCl₂ and
400 Hg(NO₃)₂ solutions at concentrations of 100 mg/L (Fig. 7) and 50 mg/L Hg²⁺ (Fig. S7). The
401 solutions initial conductivity and pH are shown in Table S3. As is clear, the speciation of the
402 solutions is very different. In acidic conditions in HgCl₂ solution the predominant species is
403 neutral soluble HgCl₂, while in Hg(NO₃)₂ solution considerable portion of mercury is in the ionic
404 forms of Hg²⁺ and HgOH⁺. This is corroborated by the conductivity measurements of the
405 solutions, found to be 13.08 μS/cm for HgCl₂ solution and 244 μS/cm for Hg(NO₃)₂ solution.
406 Note that small amounts of chloride occasionally present in lab water and may change the
407 speciation of a Hg(NO₃)₂ solution, for instance at 10 ppm chloride the amount of Hg⁺² is still
408 considerable but new species such as HgCl⁺ emerge (Fig. 7).

409

410

411

412
 413 **Fig. 7.** Speciation of 100 mg/L Hg^{2+} chloride (upper) and nitrate (middle) solutions in ultra-pure
 414 water and Hg^{2+} nitrate (bottom) solution in ultra-pure water with 10 ppm chloride impurity
 415 (Diagram created by Medusa software).

416 In SAC experiments the pH of the solutions did not change much compared to the pH of
 417 the solution with AAC, which increased to almost neutral pH (Table S3). It should be noted that
 418 although precipitation of HgO is possible according to Medusa, it was not experimentally
 419 observed. One reason is that Medusa shows only systems in equilibrium and the formation of
 420 some species may take considerable time. Also, in the course of the experiment mercury
 421 concentration is reduced, speciation changes and the precipitation either occurs in higher pH or
 422 the portion of mercury that may be precipitating becomes lower (Fig. S7).

423 One of the proposed removal mechanisms is the ion exchange process between H^+ and/or
 424 Na^+ in the cryogel phase with Hg^{2+} from the solution phase followed by Hg^{2+} complexation with
 425 the functional groups. The conductance and pH data provide some evidence of the interactions
 426 between mercury species and the cryogels surface (Table S3). The conductance of HgCl_2
 427 solution after adsorption of mercury was considerably increased by almost 10-fold, due to the
 428 simultaneous release of Na^+ and Cl^- ions after HgCl_2 interacts with the cryogels functional

429 groups. The removal of mercury from solution by AAC resulted in an increase of pH, while the
430 pH in SAC experiment remains acidic which an indication that H⁺ is released, and as expected it
431 led to the increase of the solution's conductivity. This phenomenon occurs due to the substitution
432 of hydronium from the ionic shell of the sulfonic acid with mercury ions, as it is shown in
433 reaction below (7):

435 The adsorption of Hg(NO₃)₂ solution by AAC show that, while pH evolution is the same,
436 the conductivity was decreased by a factor of 2, due to the binding of Hg²⁺. This is an indication
437 that there is a net decrease of ions in the solution; indeed, while the removal of neutral HgCl₂
438 species from the solution cannot have any substantial effect on the conductance, the removal of
439 of Hg²⁺ and HgOH⁺ leads to a decrease of conductance. Based on these observations, ion
440 exchange process between H⁺ and/or Na⁺ with Hg²⁺ is possible and in a good agreement with pH
441 and conductivity. The conductance changes depend on both the charge and the ion mobility and
442 while ion exchange is stoichiometric process, the exchange of different ions leads to considerable
443 changes in conductance; for instance, H⁺ mobility is almost 7 times this of Na⁺ [74]. However,
444 while pH and conductance are useful they cannot provide a solid proof that ion exchange is the
445 predominant mechanism. In order to further study the removal mechanism, the released Na⁺
446 from the cryogels during the interaction with mercury was studied. The Hg²⁺/Na⁺ molar ratio is
447 shown in Fig. 8 and depends on the mass of the cryogel/solution volume ratio. For many AAC
448 experimental data the molar ratio of Hg²⁺/Na⁺ ratio is close to 0.5, which is the stoichiometric
449 ratio expected if ion exchange takes place. In the case of SAC cryogel, the Hg²⁺/Na⁺ ratio is
450 much higher, which means that the released amount of Na⁺ is small. This happens due to the low

451 initial concentration of sodium ions in the SAC cryogel, but probably also because of the
452 sulfonic acid's H^+ is exchanged with Hg^{2+} as well.

453

454

455

456 **Fig. 8.** Molar ratio of removed Hg^{2+} and released Na^+ during adsorption.

457 The results show that the ion exchange mechanism is involved in both cryogels, albeit the
458 kinetics and equilibrium strongly depend on the mercury solution phase speciation and the
459 chemistry of the cryogels surface. The mechanism is probably ion exchange followed by
460 complexation of mercury species with the cryogels functional groups [46]. The FTIR spectra of
461 Hg -loaded cryogels are shown in Fig. 9. The peaks of amide (I) and amide (II) groups at 1612
462 and 1543 cm^{-1} in AAC samples are shifted to lower frequencies by 2 to 7 cm^{-1} and their intensity
463 is decreased in comparison to the parent cryogels. This indicates deprotonation or bounding of
464 mercury on the carbonyl groups [75,76]. A similar pattern of amide peaks shifting is observed in
465 the SAC samples after binding of Hg^{2+} ions. Also, the peak of sulfonic acid at 1186 cm^{-1} of the
466 parent SAC sample is shifted to 1182 and 1178 cm^{-1} in the samples $Hg(NO_3)_2$ and $HgCl_2$
467 solutions, respectively.

468

469

470

471 **Fig. 9.** FTIR patterns of cryogels before and after Hg²⁺ adsorption: A) AAC, B) SAC.

472 For in-depth investigation of the interactions on the surface of the cryogels XPS characterization
473 was done before and after the adsorption of the mercury on both cryogels and solutions (Fig. 10
474 (A,B)).

475

476

477

478

479 **Fig. 10.** XPS spectra of AAC (A) and SAC (B) cryogels before (blue curves) and after (green
480 and red curves) mercury removal

481 Three C 1s peaks were identified on both cryogels at 284.6, 286.8 and 288.2 eV
482 corresponding to C-C, C-O and C=O [77]. After the interaction with mercury, the intensity of C-

483 O and C=O peaks decreased drastically. Sulfonic acid groups show a S 2p peak at 168.2 [78],
484 close to the peak at 168.08 eV of the SAC cryogel. The S 2p peak is deconvoluted into two major
485 peaks centered at 167.5 and 169 eV which are close to the 2 p_{3/2} and 2 p_{1/2} peaks of sulfonic
486 acid identified in other studies [79]. After interaction with mercury the sulfonic acid group peaks
487 had lower intensity suggesting the formation of coordination bonds of sulfonic acid with
488 mercury. In both cryogels before the interaction with mercury, two peaks of Na 1s at 1071.4 and
489 Na_{KLL} Auger peak at 497.1 eV were observed. After the interaction with mercury ions the
490 intensity of sodium peaks decreased sharply with the advent of mercury peaks. The Hg 4f on of
491 AAC cryogel showed peaks at 101 and 105 eV attributed to Hg 4f_{7/2} and Hg 4f_{5/2}, respectively.
492 In SAC cryogel, the peaks of Hg 4f_{7/2} and Hg 4f_{5/2} were shifted to 101.25 and 105.18 eV,
493 respectively. According to these binding energies mercury is in Hg²⁺ oxidation state, supporting
494 the hypothesis of ion-exchange mechanism involving Na⁺ [80,81].

495 EDX analysis shows that the nitrogen content was decreased from 12% in the parent
496 cryogels to about 1% after the interaction with mercury (Fig. S3). However, the measurement of
497 the total nitrogen content by Dumas combustion method (Table S4) shows that there are not
498 significant changes of nitrogen content. Thus, the very low nitrogen content observed by EDX
499 after the interaction with mercury can be attributed to the coverage of the surface by mercury,
500 which is apparently masking the nitrogen on the surface. Also, this is an indication of some kind
501 of interaction between mercury and nitrogen.

502 Based on these observations, the possible complexation reactions on the surface of AAC
503 and SAC cryogels between Hg²⁺ and the carboxylic, amide and sulfonic acid groups can be
504 summarized as follows [22,23,82,83]:

509 The same phenomena were observed by Wang et al. after interaction of chitosan-p(vinyl
 510 alcohol) cryogel with Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions, where it was suggested that $-\text{NHCOCH}_3$ and $-\text{NH}_2$
 511 were involved in metal ions chelation [33]. Based on the presented removal mechanism
 512 hypothesis, the structure of the cryogels after the adsorption of Hg^{2+} is presented in Fig. 11.

513
 514
 515 **Fig.11.** Proposed complexation of Hg^{2+} ions with functional groups of AAC (A) and SAC (B)

516 cryogels.

517

518 **3.5 Mercury removal from different water matrices and by commercial adsorbents**

519 Mercury removal results from the different water matrices and materials are presented in
520 Table 4. The first 10 min of adsorption both AAC and SAC cryogels showed 20-30% removal of
521 Hg^{2+} ions from UP water, while the rest of materials removed less than 2%. In the tap and river
522 water the cryogels also showed better removal rate after 10 min of interaction; however, in
523 seawater the removal of mercury by all materials was less than 6%. After 24h in ultra-pure water
524 the AAC cryogel showed more than 90% removal, the SAC cryogel removed about 70%, while
525 the rest of commercial adsorbents eliminated no more than 33%. In tap and river water, where
526 the concentrations of co-existing cations are much higher comparing with ultra pure water (Table
527 S5), the efficiency was reduced for all materials. Nevertheless, AAC sample removed
528 approximately 77% and 87% of mercury from tap and river water, respectively. The best
529 adsorption efficiency of all used commercial sorbents was demonstrated by activated carbon,
530 which reached 47% and 35% of the mercury removal from tap and river water, respectively. The
531 natural seawater was the most complex matrix due to the large concentrations of ions. In these
532 conditions only activated carbon removed about 45% of mercury, while the rest of the materials
533 removed only 10-20% of mercury.

534 The behavior of adsorbents could be explained by taking into account the speciation of
535 mercury ions in the various water matrices. The speciation of mercury was studied by using
536 Medusa software and the real concentrations of main cations and anions in the investigated water
537 matrices (Fig. 12 and Fig. S8). In all water matrices except seawater, the main forms of mercury
538 were HgCl_2 , $\text{Hg}(\text{OH})_2$ and HgClOH , while in seawater the predominant species were HgCl_4^{2-} ,
539 HgCl_3^- , HgCl_2 . Taking into account that all materials, except activated carbon, are cation-

540 exchangers it is expected that they will not perform well under the existence of high
541 concentrations of anionic forms of mercury and competing cations found in seawater. The results
542 presented in Table S5 also confirm the proposed mechanism of mercury adsorption by AAC and
543 SAC cryogel. The concentrations of Na⁺ ions after 24 h in both cryogels and zeolites were
544 increased in ultra-pure, tap and river water, accompanied with an increase of the pH. The ion-
545 exchange resin removed Hg²⁺ by ion exchange with H⁺, which caused a decrease of pH. Finally,
546 in AAC and SAC cryogels an increase of PO₄²⁻ concentration was observed in tap, river and
547 seawater, probably a result of anion exchange with anions from the solution. Also, K⁺, Mg²⁺ and
548 Ca²⁺ were removed by all materials except activated carbon, which is an indication of ion-
549 exchange mechanism..

550 **Table 4**

551 Residual concentrations of mercury ions (mg/L) in various water matrices after interaction with
552 adsorbents at different time.

	Time (min)	10	60	240	1440
UP water	Activated carbon	9.83±0.13	9.23±0.17	9.14±0.25	7.09±0.59
	Ion-exchange resin	10.26±0.40	9.73±0.04	9.18±0.14	6.75±0.15
	Zeolite	9.82±0.08	9.66±0.40	9.12±0.13	7.81±0.07
	AAC	8.15±0.40	5.62±0.91	3.46±0.66	0.90±0.36
	SAC	6.93±0.60	4.00±0.19	1.49±0.28	0.31±0.14
	control	10.37±0.18	10.05±0.11	9.88±0.01	9.78±0.03
tap	Activated carbon	9.48±0.72	8.78±0.10	8.12±0.34	5.28±0.17
	Ion-exchange resin	9.81±1.03	9.08±0.13	9.06±0.22	8.99±0.08
	Zeolite	9.08±0.08	8.78±0.22	8.57±0.10	8.34±0.19
	AAC	8.63±0.32	6.66±0.33	5.75±1.55	2.35±1.94
	SAC	8.36±0.36	7.50±0.36	6.84±0.58	5.62±0.30
	control	9.53±0.33	9.30±0.00	9.13±0.05	9.00±0.03
river	Activated carbon	9.23±0.19	8.80±0.04	8.32±0.11	6.48±0.44
	Ion-exchange resin	9.32±0.12	8.86±0.64	8.08±0.37	7.02±0.43
	Zeolite	8.86±0.10	8.11±0.12	7.74±0.16	7.45±0.18

	AAC	7.87±0.34	5.78±0.37	3.85±0.40	1.30±1.19
	SAC	9.02±0.42	8.01±0.44	4.11±0.95	3.27±0.39
	control	9.68±0.11	9.54±0.67	9.14±0.11	9.20±0.20
seawater	Activated carbon	9.23±0.23	9.14±0.06	8.60±0.12	5.46±0.19
	Ion-exchange resin	9.55±0.04	9.56±0.04	9.41±0.06	9.14±0.03
	Zeolite	9.34±0.07	9.54±0.08	9.22±0.08	9.11±0.05
	AAC	9.40±0.05	9.44±0.04	9.22±0.13	8.41±0.30
	SAC	9.41±0.05	9.48±0.05	8.87±0.06	7.86±0.10
	Control	9.89±0.79	9.55±0.04	9.50±0.01	9.31±0.08

553

554

$[Mg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 59.10 \text{ mM}$ $[NO_3^-]_{TOT} = 0.18 \text{ mM}$
 $[K^+]_{TOT} = 9.90 \text{ mM}$ $[SO_4^{2-}]_{TOT} = 31.38 \text{ mM}$
 $[Na^+]_{TOT} = 523.00 \text{ mM}$ $[Cl^-]_{TOT} = 547.90 \text{ mM}$
 $[Hg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 50.00 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ $[Ca^{2+}]_{TOT} = 10.20 \text{ mM}$

555

$[Mg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 0.15 \text{ mM}$
 $[H^+]_{TOT} = 44.50 \text{ M}$
 $[H^+]_{TOT} = 0.88 \text{ mM}$
 $[Hg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 20.00 \text{ M}$

$[NO_3^-]_{TOT} = 0.11 \text{ mM}$
 $[PO_4^{3-}]_{TOT} = 0.14 \text{ mM}$
 $[P]_{TOT} = 0.01 \text{ mM}$
 $[Hg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 0.55 \text{ mM}$

$[Mg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 29.10 \text{ mM}$
 $[H^+]_{TOT} = 9.00 \text{ mM}$
 $[H^+]_{TOT} = 255.00 \text{ mM}$
 $[Hg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 20.00 \text{ M}$

$[NO_3^-]_{TOT} = 0.18 \text{ mM}$
 $[PO_4^{3-}]_{TOT} = 11.88 \text{ mM}$
 $[P]_{TOT} = 2.67 \text{ mM}$
 $[Hg^{2+}]_{TOT} = 10.50 \text{ mM}$

556

557 **Fig. 12.** Speciation of 10 mg/L Hg in river (top) and seawater (bottom) matrices (diagrams were
558 created by Medusa software).

559 **4. Conclusions**

560 Two novel cryogels were synthesized, characterized and studied for the removal of Hg^{2+}
561 from $Hg(NO_3)_2$ and $HgCl_2$ solutions. The results showed rapid removal kinetics and high
562 equilibrium capacity for both cryogels, with AAC cryogel being superior over SAC cryogel. The
563 removal of Hg^{2+} is higher in $Hg(NO_3)_2$ solution due to the ionic mercury species which are

564 diffusing and interacting faster and more efficiently with the cryogels functional groups. The
565 AAC and SAC samples showed maximum removal capacity of 260 mg/g for HgCl₂ solution and
566 620 mg/g for g(NO₃)₂ solution. The Hg²⁺ removal mechanism is most probably ion exchange
567 followed by complexation reactions. The results of the removal of mercury from different real
568 water matrices (ultra-pure water, tap water and river water) show that cryogels exhibit much
569 faster kinetics than commercial adsorbents (activated carbon, strong acid resin and zeolite Y)
570 with the exception of seawater, where activated carbon was superior.

571

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577

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